

Shodhana of Bhallataka (Rasatarangini): A Pharmaceutical Study

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ABSTRACT:-

➤ Background:

Bhallataka is a toxic drug which comes under *Upavisha Varga* according to classical texts in *Rasashastra*. But its have so many properties, that makes it to use in various diseases. *Ashuddha Bhallataka* can cause the toxic effects but when it goes under the *Samskara* i.e. *Shodhana* procedure it plays important role in therapeutic values. Due to the presence of Tarry oil which when comes in direct contact to the skin it forms the blisters, itching and all other side effects to the body. So, there are the fear factors when to deal with toxic drugs. Specially the precautionary methods which should be follow and the knowledge of antidots for the particular one. Different Acharya have mentioned various *Shodhana* methods for the *Bhallataka* with different media. Media plays a very important role in reducing the toxicity and with particular media enhancing its properties. So, in this study an attempt has been done for *Shodhana* of *Bhallataka* by taking all the precautionary and observation study being made to reduce the errors in further.

➤ Aim:

To do the Pharmaceutical study for *Shodhana* of *Bhallataka*.

➤ Material and Methods:

Ashuddha Bhallataka was taken from Sundar Ayurveda Pharmacy, Nadiad. *Shodhana* Procedure was done according to the reference mentioned in *Rasatarangini*. *Narikela Jala* and *Godugdha* were used as media. All the equipments and precautions were taken during the procedure.

➤ Results:

Yield of *Shuddha Bhallataka* after *Shodhana* with both media was 52.9 % . After so many precautions still it showed the toxic effects itching all over body and red patches all over the skin.

➤ Conclusion:

So, this study deals with the parameters used in the pharmaceutical study from which you can get the idea how to do it as per the classical text and can get the *Shuddha Bhallataka* . Also precautionary methods to be followed and if there are toxic effects so how we can overcome to them.

Keywords: *Bhallataka, Shodhana, Narikela Jala, Godugdha, Rasatarangini.*

I. INTRODUCTION

According to *Ayurveda*, there is no substance in the world which cannot be used as medicine. Most of the drugs, as such cannot be used for the therapeutic purpose in the biological systems. Hence, to develop an elegant, compatible & convenient dosages forms, which can be applied easily, will be the need of time. These specific modifications are known as '*Samskara*' in *Ayurveda*, and they can be grouped under the headings of 'Pharmaceutical Processes' in contemporary languages.

Behind all the pharmaceutical procedures, *Shodhana* has its prime importance, because it is the *Shodhana* by which we can use poisonous substances as medicine. By the process of *Shodhana*, the virtues of properties of *Shodhana Dravyas* are inherited into a substance.

So, it has become our prime duty to establish the proper *Shodhana* method in the scientific way in regards to get specific therapeutic effect and get maximum yield as well fulfilling all necessary parameters to make that substance best therapeutic.

The prime objective of pharmaceutical study is to develop a safe, effective and quality drug. Efficacy and safety depend solely on the quality of the drug and their proper processing.

Different Acharyas have mentioned different media and methods for *Shodhana* of *Bhallataka* in different *Ayurvedic* classics. Here, we have adopted the *Rasatarangini* method for *Shodhana* by using two media (*Narikela Jala* & *Godugdha*).¹ So, this study dealt with Pharmaceutical procedure for *Shodhana* of *Bhallataka*.

II. MATERIAL AND METHODS

➤ Procurement of Raw Drugs:

Bhallataka was procured in amount of 1.5 Kg from Sundar Ayurved Pharmacy, JSAM, Nadiad.

➤ Equipments and Instruments:

Weighing balance, *Dola Yantra*, Cloth, Measuring Jar, Heating device, Knife, Cutter, Tray, Thermometer, Pyrometer, Measuring scale, Gloves, Mask.

➤ Reference:

ÉLItk)lanlhnairkelaMbuyægt> , iSvNnaindaailkayNÇzñmayaNtynuÄmam,, (Rasatarangini 24/479)

➤ Principle: Swedana

Table 1 Showing Ingredients used for *Shodhana* of *Bhallataka*

Sr. No.	Ingredients	Part used	Quantity
1	<i>Ashuddha Bhallataka</i> (g)	Fruit	1500
2	<i>Narikela Jala</i> (ml)	-	3300
3	<i>Godugdha</i> (ml)	-	3300

➤ Procedure:

- Caps were removed from *Ashuddha Bhallataka* and cut into pieces.
- *Pottali* was prepared with use of clean cotton cloth.
- *Narikela Jala* was filled into *Dola Yantra* and *Pottali* was hanged into it.
- Boiling was done on mild heat for 3hrs.
- Obtained pieces of *Bhallataka* were washed with warm water.
- Then, again the same procedure was followed by using *Godugdha* as media instead of *Narikela Jala*.
- Obtained pieces of *Bhallataka* were washed with warm water.
- *Shuddha Bhallataka* was dried in shade and collected.

➤ Showing Plate for *Shodhana* of *Bhallataka*:

- Plate for *Shodhana* of *Bhallataka*

Fig 2 Removed Caps

Fig 1 Removal of Caps from *Ashuddha Bhallataka* and Cut into Pieces

Fig 3 Preparation of Pottali

Fig 4 Hanging of Pottali into Dola Yantra

Fig 7 Preparation of Pottali

Fig 5 Filling of Narikela Jala into Dola Yantra and continuous heat for 3hrs

Fig 8 Hanging of Pottali into Dola Yantra

Fig 6 Wash it with warm water and Shuddha Bhallataka collected

Fig 9 Filling of Godugdha into Dola Yantra

Fig 10 Continuous Heat for 3hrs

Fig 12 Dried in Shade and Collected

Fig 11 Wash it with Warm Water

➤ *Observations:*

- The colour of *Narikela Jala* was turned from transparent to dark brown blackish whereas *Godugdha* was turned from white to creamish brown in colour.
- Consistency of *Narikela Jala* and *Godugdha* found increase during procedure.
- Characteristic smell of *Narikela Jala* and *Godugdha* felt throughout procedure.
- After *Shodhana Bhallataka* became soft.

Table 2 Showing Temperature Pattern of Flame, *Narikela Jala*, *Godugdha* in *Shodhana* of *Bhallataka*

Sr.No.	Duration (h:min)	Temperature (°C)			
		Flame		<i>Narikela Jala</i>	<i>Godugdha</i>
		NKSB	GDSB	NKSB	GDSB
1	0:00	335	330	22	24
2	0:30	338	335	97	103
3	1:00	330	333	104	105
4	1:30	335	335	106	104
5	2:00	335	340	105	107
6	2:30	340	342	108	111
7	3:00	340	335	110	113

III. RESULTS

Table 3 Showing Pharmaceutical Results in *Shodhana* of *Bhallataka*

Sr.No.	Parameters for <i>Bhallataka</i>	Results
1	Wt of <i>Ashuddha Bhallataka</i> (g)	1500
2	Wt of <i>Ashuddha Bhallataka</i> after removing cap(g)	850
3	Wt of <i>Bhallataka</i> after <i>Shodhana</i> with <i>Narikela Jala</i> (NKSB) (g)	827
4	Weight loss of <i>Bhallataka</i> after <i>Shodhana</i> (g)	673
5	Yield of <i>Bhallataka</i> after <i>Shodhana</i> (%)	55.1
6	Wt of <i>Bhallataka</i> after <i>Shodhana</i> with <i>Godugdha</i> (GDSB) (g)	794
7	Weight loss of <i>Bhallataka</i> after <i>Shodhana</i> (g)	33
8	Yield of <i>Shuddha Bhallataka</i> after <i>Shodhana</i> with both media (%)	52.9
Parameters for <i>Narikela Jala</i> and <i>Godugdha</i>		
1	<i>Narikela Jala</i> used for <i>Shodhana</i> (ml)	3300
2	<i>Narikela Jala</i> left after <i>Shodhana</i> (ml)	2500
3	Volume loss after <i>Shodhana</i> (ml)	800

4	Volume Loss (%)	24.24
5	Godugdha used for Shodhana (ml)	3300
6	Godugdha left after Shodhana (ml)	2650
7	Volume loss after Shodhana (ml)	650
8	Volume Loss (%)	19.69

➤ **Precautions:**

- *Pottali* should be completely immersed in the media and should not touch the bottom of vessel.
- The Quantity of media should maintained to keep *Pottali* immersed into it throughout the procedure.
- Gloves and Mask should be wear to avoid the inhalation of toxic fumes.

IV. DISCUSSION

Shodhana for *Bhallataka* was done according to Rasatarangini reference in which the media is said to be taken *Narikela Jala*. But when we go through the Vaktavya mentioned in it. It is clearly said that if *Bhallataka* is not purified then this procedure can be continued by taking *Godugdha* as media. And whole procedure is repeated with taking principle and duration is same.

During procedures general precautionary methods have to be taken is must but there are some other factors too which can cause the errors as per *Dravya* , *Prakriti*, *Ritu*, *Kala*, *Bala*, *Satva*, *Aahara* and *Vihara*.

Shodhana was done by fully covered, *Narikela* oil was applied all over the body, continuously 3 to 4 litres of *Narikela Jala* was consumed during all days of procedure still red patches all over the skin and itching occurred over the body for a long period.

V. CONCLUSION

Bhallataka is a toxic drug but when undergoes purification procedure it can be used for therapeutic purposes.

Precautions should be taken especially when you are dealing with *Bhallataka*.

➤ *Different Type of Experiences can be Felt or they can be vary as per the Individual:*

- Toxicity study should be done for seeing accuracy results.
- Dose , Antidot and *Anupana* plays a very important role in subsiding the effects.
- So, it is very important to follow proper procedure and precautions for the *Shodhana* of *Bhallataka*.

REFERENCES

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